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Technika a vzdelávanie

Časopis zameraný na technické vzdelávanie v základných, stredných, i na vysokých školách, na oblasť základného a aplikovaného výskumu, aplikáciu informačných technológií vo výučbe odborných predmetov.

ÚVODNÍK

Vážené čitateľky, vážení čitatelia,

s potešením Vám predstavujeme druhé tohtoročné číslo časopisu *Technika a vzdelávanie*, ktorý v roku 2025 vstupuje do svojho už štrnásteho ročníka. Táto skutočnosť je pre nás nielen dôvodom byť hrdí, ale aj potvrdením toho, že dlhodobé vzájomné spájanie myšlienok podpory technického vzdelávania má stále zmysel. Isteže, aj tentoraz v ňom nájdete zaujímavé príspevky odrážajúce aktivity, skúsenosti zo zahraničia, inšpiratívne príklady z praxe, novinky či reporty z výsledkov riešenia projektov autorov príspevkov. Ved' čo iné nás motivuje v našom časopise si zalistovať?

V poslednom čase sa nám však jasne ukazuje, že bolo potrebné prijať aktívnejší editorský prístup, ktorý spočíva v premyslenejšom výbere, úprave a inovovanom zoraďovaní príspevkov. Pristúpili sme k tomu, že do časopisu zahrňame aj príspevky so špecifickým charakterom, a to v presvedčení, že sa stanú v blízkej budúcnosti témou diskusie na spoločných fórach našej komunity.

V tomto čísle sa venujeme viacerým oblastiam, avšak nosnými témami ostávajú najmä príspevky venované technickému vzdelávaniu, ktoré prechádza v posledných rokoch dynamickými zmenami na všetkých stupňoch škôl - od základných až po vysoké. V tomto čísle sa niektoré príspevky venujú aj konkrétnym príkladom z reálnej praxe, ktoré ukazujú skutočnosť, že tímová spolupráca či prepájanie prírodovedného a technického vzdelávania je cestou, ktorá dokáže osloviť aj tých žiakov, ktorí sa doteraz v tejto oblasti nenašli. Rovnako inšpiratívne sú reporty z výsledkov podujatí a súťaží, ktoré potvrdzujú, že mladí ľudia majú veľký potenciál, tvorivosť a chuť riešiť technické problémy, čo prebúdzajú ich záujem o odbory, ktoré sú pre modernú spoločnosť kľúčové. Nechýbajú ani odborné pohľady a analýzy, ktoré ovplyvňujú priemyselnú prax a podporujú diskusiu o potrebe prípravy mladej generácie na budúcnosť, v ktorej technika bude zohrávať ešte významnejšiu úlohu ako dnes.

Veríme, že články, ktoré prinášame v tomto čísle, podporia odbornú diskusiu a budú kvalitnou inšpiráciou - či už pri tvorbe vyučovacích aktivít, pri zavádzaní nových didaktických metód a prístupov alebo pri budovaní stále spomínanej spolupráce medzi školou a praxou.

Z pozície šéfredaktora a v mene celej redakčnej rady časopisu Vám ďakujem za štrnásť rokov dôvery, spätnej väzby i tvorivej energie. Prajem mnoho úspechov, nekončiacej inšpirácie do svojej práce, a najmä pevné zdravie.

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CYBERHATE AND ITS IMPACT ON ADOLESCENTS

A LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

The rapid development of digital technology in recent decades has brought about significant changes in the way people communicate. Despite its multiple benefits, online communication involves risks, until recently unknown, which have become the subject of increasing scientific interest. Among these are "cyberbullying" and "cyberhate." While the former has been extensively studied, the phenomenon of cyberhate, or hate speech on the internet, namely digital content that incites hatred and violence against vulnerable individuals or groups, remains largely unexplored in research. The present paper aims, through a review of recent literature, to highlight critical aspects of this phenomenon, focusing on the vulnerable and crucial age of adolescence.

Key words: cyberhate, internet, literature review

Introduction

Research data demonstrate the global nature of cyberhate (Reichelmann et al., 2020; Wachs, Costello et al., 2021; Wachs, Mazzone et al., 2021), as well as the constantly increasing prevalence among adolescents (Hawdon, Bernatzky, & Costello, 2019). In Greece, a recent online survey conducted with a sample of 4,800 adolescents revealed that 80% of participants were not familiar with the meaning of the term "hate speech", 25% reported having been victims of online hate attacks, and 45% stated that they had witnessed such incidents (Greek Safer Internet Center, 2024). The findings of this study are in line with corresponding results from international research, although significant differences are observed between countries, both in the frequency of the phenomenon and in the policy interventions adopted (Fulantelli et al., 2022; Wachs, Costello et al., 2021; Wachs, Mazzone et al., 2021).

During adolescence, young people are in the process of shaping their personal identity and defining their role within the social sphere. In this context, in order to be accepted by their peer group and to feel a sense of belonging, they may adopt aggressive behaviors, both in the physical and the digital world. Those behaviors include online hate attacks. At the same time, adolescents are more vulnerable than adults to indoctrination by online "merchants" of hate, as these individuals offer them a political and social identity, as well as a sense of belonging—something they may not be able to find in other groups (Wachs, Costello et al., 2021). On the other hand, adolescents who experience aggressive and intolerant behaviors are difficult for them to cope with, due to their age and limited experience, they have not yet sufficiently developed critical thinking or the necessary psychological defense mechanisms (Fulantelli et al., 2022; Pyrgianaki et al., 2025).

The exposure of adolescents to online hate speech, whether as victims, observers, or even perpetrators, has significant negative effects on their mental health and overall well-being (Reichelmann et al., 2020; Armakolas et al., 2024). Such experiences often lead to increased levels of anxiety, stress, and depression, undermining their

healthy psychosocial development. For this reason, it is important to investigate the factors that render adolescents vulnerable to victimization through cyberhate, as well as those that drive them to engage as perpetrators or to remain passive bystanders. Understanding these factors contributes to the design of appropriate and effective programs for the prevention and management of digital hate. Adolescents' exposure to hate speech online, whether as victims, bystanders or even perpetrators, has significant negative impacts on their mental health and overall well-being (Reichelmann et al., 2020).

In these terms, psychoeducational programs should focus not only on risk factors but also on effective intervention strategies that adolescents can employ, thereby strengthening their psychological resilience against online hate. After all, adolescents spend a significant portion of their daily lives connected to the internet (Feierabend et al., 2018, as cited in Wachs, Costello et al., 2021, p. 2), which increases their likelihood of exposure to intolerant speech and online attacks. Protecting adolescents from such phenomena thus becomes imperative.

1.1 Conceptual Clarification

Nowadays, teenagers become witnesses of online hate "content," which has adverse effects on their mental health (Reichelmann et al., 2020). However, despite the seriousness of the phenomenon, the scientific community has not yet reached a commonly accepted definition of cyberhate, making it difficult to compare data from related studies and to draw reliable conclusions regarding its nature and effective management (Jimenez-Diaz & Del Rey, 2025).

Literature mentions multiple definitions that are used as synonymous terms to cyberhate that are often used as synonyms for cyberhate, such as "online hate speech" or "online hate content/material" (Jimenez-Diaz & Del Rey, 2025). However, recent research highlights the need not only to clarify but also to broaden the concept of cyberhate. In this context, Jimenez-Diaz and Del Rey (2025, p.8) consider cyberhate to be a broader phenomenon than hate speech. More specifically, those terms define cyberhate as "any form of online hate, in the form of text, audiovisual content, memes, rumors, etc.,

directed at an individual or groups of individuals that harms, humiliates, and/or promotes hatred and hostility towards them". This definition does not include hate attacks based on the stigmatization of various social groups according to gender, ethnicity, origin, religion, sexual orientation, or disability, which fall within the scope of traditional hate speech. Moreover, research indicates that there are no clear motives behind many instances of online hate (Kaakinen, Keipi et al., 2018, as cited in Jimenez-Diaz & Del Rey, 2025, p. 8), while motives such as publicity or physical appearance can trigger hate posts, even though they do not fall within the conventional definition of hate speech.

Despite the fact that recent indicators show that cyberhate doesn't affect specific social groups (Costello et al., 2017, as it is stated by Jimenez-Diaz & Del Rey, 2025, p.8), the majority of researchers This dimension is considered crucial for clarifying the concept (e.g., Blaya & Audrin, 2019; Wachs & Wright, 2021). Indeed, it is argued that the main difference between cyberbullying and cyberhate lies in the fact that, in the former, perpetrators target specific individuals, whom they systematically and repeatedly intimidate—not because of hatred toward the social group to which the victims belong. In contrast, cyberhate is directed at individuals or groups precisely because of their social identity and can occur even in a single incident. In this case, main goal is the incitement of hatred and violence against these individuals based on characteristics related to their social identity (Wachs & Wright, 2021), as well as the involvement of multiple perpetrators in the attack (Fulantelli et al., 2022). However, the necessity for a broader term which will include the different diverse forms of aggressive behavior remains imperative in the online environment. In this context, Grigg (2010, as cited in Fulantelli et al., 2022, p. 2) proposes the inclusive term "cyber aggression," which encompasses various forms of digital attacks, including cyberbullying, online hate speech, and cyberhate. In the present paper, however, we examine cyberhate in its broader sense, which also includes online hate speech attacks directed at specific vulnerable social groups, motivated by ideological and/or political reasons.

1.2 Risk factors

The literature identifies various factors associated with victimization, perpetration, and adolescents' exposure to online hate content. Among those most frequently mentioned and related to the individual characteristics of those involved are: excessive use of the Internet and social media, the disclosure of personal information to strangers, the search for intense experiences, deliberate navigation of websites with hostile or violent content, moral desensitization, and the attempt to satisfy the sense of "belonging" to a group (Jimenez-Diaz & Del Rey, 2025). However, distinguishing the factors that drive adolescents to engage in online hate attacks from those that make them victims of such attacks is often difficult, as research has shown that the roles of perpetrator, victim, and bystander in online hate frequently alternate and overlap (Wachs, Costello et al., 2021; Wachs & Wright, 2021).

Empirical data indicate that adolescents who are systematically exposed to or victimized by online hate tend to perceive it as something "normal," which increases the likelihood that they will also engage in such behavior themselves (Bedrosova et al., 2023, as cited in Jimenez-Diaz & Del Rey, 2025, p. 9).

Moreover, there is evidence that adolescents with a migratory background who have experienced online hate often appear as perpetrators of intolerant aggression, in an attempt to "strengthen their identity by devaluing other groups" (Castellanos et al., 2023, p. 12). It seems that adolescents belonging to vulnerable social groups often engage in acts of hate speech both online and offline as a way of coping with the intense negative emotions they experience due to the intolerant behaviors directed at them (Obermaier & Schmyck, 2022).

It is also important to emphasize the psychosocial dimension of the phenomenon and the influence of peer groups on the adoption of online hate behaviors, which is an area that has not yet been extensively researched (Jimenez-Diaz & Del Rey, 2025).

Several studies have focused on the role of parents in their children's victimization or involvement in online hate. Specifically, practices such as posting and sharing personal photos and information about their children online (sharenting) increase the likelihood that these children will become targets of hate attacks. Furthermore, restrictive or reactive strategies employed by parents to deal with cyberhate appear to be associated with a higher risk of victimization (Jimenez-Diaz & Del Rey, 2025; Koral & Braya, 2025; Wachs, Costello et al., 2021). The need for parental education on how to protect and support their children, particularly adolescents, against online aggression and, more specifically, online hate, is therefore imperative (Armakolas, et al., 2025).

Finally, beyond parental strategies to protect their children when they have been victims of online hate or attacks, research has also highlighted adolescents' own strategies that either increase or reduce the likelihood of involvement in such phenomena. Specifically, empirical findings suggest that retaliatory responses to online hate are associated with increased victimization, whereas assertive strategies are linked to reduced victimization (Jimenez-Diaz & Del Rey, 2025; Wachs & Wright, 2021).

The last years, many researchers in their attempt to understand and explain the reasons why certain individuals become victims of online hate, have drawn on the Routine Activity Theory (RAT; Cohen & Felson, 1979, as cited in Wachs, Mazzone et al., 2021, p. 2). Even though this theory originally developed within the field of criminology, it has been applied to the study of cyberbullying and online hate (Obermaier & Schmuck, 2022). According to this study, there are three key factors that are related to an increased likelihood victimization from cyberhate attacks. These include the individual's own actions that render them vulnerable and make them a target, such as communicating with strangers and sharing personal information, the ineffective supervision by parents or other adults, and frequent exposure to online risks such as the search for intense sensations (sensation

seeking), engagement with hate speech online, and digital addiction (Wachs, Costello et al., 2021; Wachs, Mazzone et al., 2021). Therefore, according to this theory, adolescents' everyday risky online behaviors are positively associated with their victimization from cyberhate.

2.1 Theoretical grounding of cyberhate perpetration

At the same time, the same researchers suggest the use of the Problem Behaviour Theory (PBT; Jesson & Jesson, 1977, as cited in Wachs, Mazzone et al., 2021, p. 3) is also relevant. Although originally developed to explain addiction, it has been applied to the understanding of online aggression. PBT represents a systemic approach, according to which adolescents' so-called "problematic" behaviors are interpreted through the lens of the interaction between individual, environmental, and social factors. In the case of cyberhate, the theory supports that adolescents' perpetrators often tend to engage in risky online behaviors in search of intense emotions, use social media excessively, and trust strangers online (Wachs, Mazzone et al., 2021). It is evident that Online hate perpetrators often seek their identity in dangerous online paths, which may make them not only would-be perpetrators, but also potential victims of hate attacks. Moreover, the General Strain Theory which was developed by Roberd Agnew (1992), supports that the psychological pressure that adolescents feel when they deal with stressful situations can lead to aggressive behaviours. In the case of cyberhate, adolescents attack with hate material online as a reaction or defence to the discomfort they feel when encountering or receiving hate attacks (Audrin & Blaya, 2024).

2.2 Protective Factors

Audrin & Blaya (2024) in a recent study of French students aged 9-17 found that one of the most important protective factors against committing online hate crimes is support from family and teachers. It appears that parents who maintain a close relationship with their children and adopt a guiding role help prevent their involvement in online hate incidents (Wright, Wachs, & Gámez-Guadix, 2021). Furthermore, diverse personal characteristics of adolescents, such as high level of self-esteem, assertiveness and belief in self-efficacy in problem solving (Wachs et al., 2023), as well as mental resilience (Wachs, Gamez-Guadix, & Wright, 2022) are negatively related to victimization and engagement in hate speech behaviours. Finally, research data shows that adolescents who have developed digital skills are less involved in online hate speech attacks, while also dealing with them more effectively (Wachs & Wright, 2021). According to Festl (2021), as Obermaier & Schmuck, 2022, refer p.4), digital literacy includes skills for autonomous navigation, understanding how to use digital tools, and understanding the effects of online behavior on others. These skills act as a protective barrier against online hate (Obermaier & Schmuck, 2022).

2.3 Implications

Research data support that adolescents are constantly confronted with hateful content online, but also in the physical space (e.g. Castellanos et al., 2023; Fulantelli et al., 2022), with negative consequences on their mental health and well-being (Reichelmann et al., 2020). The effects of cyberhate can be either direct or indirect. In the first case, the teenager who is the victim of hate attacks online experiences the consequences of harassment, as in cyberbullying, such as anxiety, fear, insecurity, post-traumatic stress and a sense of helplessness (Fulantelli et al., 2022; Reichelmann et al., 2020). Moreover, victimization from exposure to hate material online is positively associated with depressive symptoms in adolescents, while resilience appears to moderate this effect (Wachs, Gámez-Guadix, & Wright, 2022). In the second case, when an adolescent becomes witnesses online hatred against the group to which he belongs, the consequences are indirect and may equally affect his mental mood and state. In that case, feelings of anger, hatred, sadness and shame are observed on people who are exposed regularly to hate material online, which burdens their mental health (Reichelmann et al., 2020). Of note is that indirect hate speech can take on uncontrolled dimensions, through inciting other individuals to act against vulnerable social groups (Fulantelli et al., 2022). To this extent, phenomena of online hate speech may cause significant negative consequences for social cohesion and trust, increasing hate crimes, racist attacks and the spread of intolerant prejudices and ideologies (Soral et al., 2018). Finally, the need to further investigate the psychological and social impact of cyberhate on adolescents is underlined as it is observed significant research gap in this field.

3 Strategies for dealing with cyberhate by adolescents and their effectiveness.

According to Lazarus & Folkman (1987) and as it is also referred to Wright, Wachs, & Gamez-Guadix, 2021, p.2), coping stressful situations by the individual concerns the ability to "reduce or eliminate their negative effects through cognitive, emotional and behavioral efforts." Those people clearly state that the existence of different existence of two different ways of dealing with stressful events: problem-focused coping strategies and emotion-focused coping strategies. Regarding the first case, the person tries to deal with the problem, showing confidence in his self-efficacy, while in the second he adopts a passive and guilty attitude, feeling overwhelmed by his negative emotions.

The model is also known as Transactional Model of Stress and Coping has used to explain the strategies for managing negative emotions of adolescents who are exposed to hate speech online. According to Frydenberg (2009, as cited in Wachs, Machimbarrena et al., 2022, p.2), we can distinguish three categories of strategies. More specifically, those that involve other people, such as friends, parents, teachers or specialists, those related to a constructive way of coping (technical and assertive

strategies) and those related to a non-constructive way (revenge, feelings of helplessness, guilt).

More specifically, it has observed that adolescents who use problem-focused strategies, such as seeking support from an adult, reporting the incident to the platform, blocking the perpetrator, deleting hateful material, saving evidence, and using counter-speech without exposing oneself to risk, are more likely to mitigate the negative emotional impact caused by online hate attacks (Wachs, Machimbarrena et al., 2022). At the same time, those technical and assertive strategies can also reduce the risk of a victim becoming a perpetrator of online hate content (Wachs & Wright, 2021; Wachs et al., 2019). Conversely, strategies such as ignoring harassment and retaliating increase the risk of re-exposure and engagement in online hate (Wachs, Machimbarrena et al., 2022). It is therefore particularly important to educate adolescents on effective strategies for dealing with hate speech online, as their involvement as perpetrators or victims of hate speech may be related to their inability to appropriately manage relevant incidents. (Wachs, Machimbarrena et al., 2022; Papanikou et al., 2023).

At the same time, it is considered equally important to inform and educate parents on issues related to the effective management of hate speech, both in the physical and the digital environment. Regarding this matter, the research has shown that parents who adopt a supportive and advisory role toward their children concerning online hate, and who are digitally literate, contribute to its effective management by encouraging them to use problem-focused coping strategies. In contrast, an authoritarian parenting style, combined with restrictive and controlling strategies regarding internet use, hinders the development of effective skills for managing aggressive behaviors in cyberspace (Wright et al., 2021).

4 Psychoeducational prevention and intervention programs

The last years, of note is the increase in hate material online, with teenagers being exposed to it on a systematic basis. This systematic exposure poses serious risks to their emotional and psychosocial development (Reichelmann et al., 2020). However, there is a lack of prevention and intervention programs against hate speech in both digital and physical spaces, as well as a limited number of studies examining the effectiveness of existing ones. In one such study, Wachs, Krause, Wright, & Gámez-Guadix (2023) evaluated the effectiveness of the hate speech prevention program for adolescents in Germany: "HateLess: Together against Hatred." The program aimed to train students in empathy, self-efficacy, and counter-narrative skills, showing significant positive results. Multiple studies note general guidelines for the design of appropriate online hate prevention and intervention programs, to which a brief reference is made. Furthermore, the literature review finds the need to educate adolescents on safe internet navigation skills, as well as effective strategies for managing online attacks and hate material. Those strategies include seeking support from an adult, reporting to the relevant platforms, blocking, not communicating

with strangers, protecting personal data, safe assertive behavior, as well as cultivating ethical use of digital media (Wachs & Wright, 2021).

One particularly effective strategy which is implemented in the case of bullying is educating adolescents to take on a "mentor" role and utilizing them as positive role models and supportive allies within the school community (peer-to-peer education, peer mentoring) has proven effective (Wachs & Wright, 2021). At the same time, strengthening the role of bystanders has proven to be crucial in preventing school bullying. Bystanders' passivity in the face of online hate speech incidents can contribute to the "normalization" of aggressive behavior and encourage violence from more perpetrators. To this extent, adolescents should be trained not to reproduce hate speech online, as well as to support themselves and the victims of such behaviors (Wachs et al., 2019).

Through the review of the relevant literature, it became clear that it is equally important to educate parents in the effective management of online hate through corresponding programs. It is observed that many parents frequently, unbeknownst to them, use ineffective strategies to protect their children from online aggression and exposure to hate speech online (Wachs, Costello et al., 2021; Wright, Wachs, & Gamez-Guadix, 2021), while at the same time online habits such as sharing pictures and personal information for themselves and their children can increase the risk of exposure to and victimization from hate material online (Wachs, Costello et al., 2021; Wachs, Mazzone et al., 2021).

Finally, research findings highlight the need for holistic psychoeducational programs that aim not only to prevent online hate but also to address other forms of aggression against adolescents, both in the physical world (bullying, hate speech) and in the digital environment (cyberbullying, cyber aggression) (Fulantelli et al., 2022).

In addition to the necessity of implementing prevention and intervention programs against online hate in schools and within communities, it is crucial that online platforms themselves undertake active measures to address hate content. Social networking sites have recently realized this necessity and are trying in various ways to prevent hate speech, such as by setting compliance rules or implementing "redirect" methods. More specifically, people who make intolerant comments are either deleted from the platform, their comments are modified, or they are redirected to selected, reliable, anti-racist material (videos, articles, memes) that provides scientific information on the issues they comment on (Windisch, Wiedlitzka, & Olaghere, 2020).

Finally, artificial intelligence could be used as a supportive tool for the detection and management of online hate speech, despite the existing technical and ethical challenges, provided that human oversight is ensured (Windisch, Wiedlitzka, & Olaghere, 2020).

Conclusion

In the present study, a literature-based investigation was conducted on the contemporary issue of online hate among adolescents. At the beginning, an attempt was

made to conceptually clarify the term, and the necessity of establishing a universally accepted definition was emphasized, in order to enable the comparison of data and the drawing of reliable conclusions across related studies. In this context, recent research findings suggest broadening the term to include a wider range of online hate behaviors. Subsequently, attention was given to the risk factors associated with both the perpetration of and victimization from online hate, as well as to the theoretical models that support and explain them. The Routine Activity Theory and the Problem Behaviour Theory explain, respectively, victimization and involvement in online hate behaviors. Subsequently, protective factors were presented, along with effective coping strategies employed by adolescents. In these terms, factors that act protectively were presented as well as effective coping strategies employed by adolescents were also discussed. Based on research findings, guidelines have been proposed for future psychoeducational prevention and intervention programs in schools, with an emphasis on digital literacy and family support. Finally, the need for online interventions by the platforms themselves against hate material and attacks, the existence of appropriate legislative regulations that respect human rights and freedom of speech, as well as the use of artificial intelligence in this direction, with the condition of human supervision, was highlighted.

Despite the fact that questions are addressed regarding the violation of the right to freedom of speech and the possible existence of political or social motives behind it, it becomes necessary to establish legislative measures that protect individuals - especially minors - from online hate, as it can have serious and adverse effects on their everyday lives.

The available research literature examining adolescents' coping strategies towards online hate is limited and fragmented. Further studies are required in this field, as their findings could play a crucial role in designing more effective prevention and intervention programs.

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